

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cyanide in Biological Samples using A New Reagent

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A new sensitive spectrophotometric determination of cyanide in polluted river water and biological samples is described. Cyanides converted into cyanogenbromide reacts with pyridine to give glutaconic aldehyde which is subsequently condensed with sulphanilic acid to give a yellowish orange coloured dye. Beer's law is obeyed at 460 nm in the range of 5–30 μg of cyanide per 10 ml of the final solution (0.5–3 ppm). The optimum reaction conditions and other important analytical parameters have been investigated. The present method is successfully applied for the analysis of cyanide in blood and urine.

CYANIDES are widely used in electroplating, in precious metal refining, manufacture of organic chemicals, and in many other processes¹. Hydrocyanic acid is used extensively as a fumigant for food storage, plants, buildings and holds of cargo ships². Cyanides are highly toxic. After absorption in the body they inactivate the enzymes and prevent utilisation of oxygen carried by the blood³. The recommended¹ maximum allowable concentration of cyanide is 5 mg m⁻³ of air calculated as CN. Because of the extreme toxicity of cyanides the World Health Organisation recommended that water containing more than 0.01 ppm of cyanide (as CN) should be rejected as unfit for public use⁴. Spectrophotometric methods for determination of cyanides are far superior than the other methods^{5–9} such as titrimetric, polarographic and chromatographic. Standard methods^{10,11} for the estimation of cyanide in effluents and in waters are based on the colorimetric procedure developed by Aldridge^{5,6} and Epstein⁷, in which cyanides are converted into cyanogen bromide which reacts with pyridine to form glutaconic aldehyde. This glutaconic aldehyde is subsequently condensed with benzidine⁸ and phenylenediamine¹² to give coloured polymethine dyes. Due to the toxicity of benzidine and *p*-phenylenediamine their use is undesirable. Several spectrophotometric methods^{13–15} have been reported in literature based on the discharge of colour of metal complexes by removal of cyanide complexes. Recently, anthranilic acid has been recommended as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of cyanide¹⁶. The present method is much more sensitive than the anthranilic acid method.

In the present communication, a new sensitive spectrophotometric method of determination of cyanide in biological samples is reported. The method is based on the conversion of cyanide to cyanogen bromide by the addition of saturated

bromine water and then reacted with pyridine to give glutaconic aldehyde. This aldehyde so formed is condensed with sulphanilic acid to give yellowish orange coloured dye, having λ_{max} at 460 nm. The other important analytical parameters have been investigated. The method is successfully applied for analysis of cyanide in blood and urine samples.

Experimental

A ECIL GS-865 spectrophotometer and a Carl-Zeiss Spekol were used with 1 cm matched glass cells. Calibrated glasswares were used for volumetric measurements.

A stock solution of cyanide was prepared by dissolving potassium cyanide (A.R.; 0.1 g) in demineralised water (100 ml). The working standards were prepared by appropriate dilution. Pyridine reagent¹⁷ was prepared by mixing concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml) and freshly distilled pyridine (18 ml). It was further diluted with demineralised water (12 ml). A 0.3% (w/v) solution of sulphanilic acid was prepared in demineralised water. Saturated bromine water was used. Solution of foreign ions were prepared using AnalaR grade chemicals.

Procedure: An aliquot (5–30 μg , 0.5–3 ppm) of cyanide sample was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask. To it saturated bromine water (0.3 ml) was added and kept for 1 min for complete bromination. The excess bromine was destroyed by dropwise addition of sodium arsenite solution. Then pyridine reagent (0.3 ml) was added to it followed by the addition of sulphanilic acid (1 ml). The resulting solution was thoroughly shaken and kept for 5–10 min for full colour development. The volume was made upto the mark with demineralised water and the absorbance measured at 460 nm against distilled water as reference. The reagent

blank was prepared in the same manner which gave no colour under these conditions.

Results and Discussion

The yellowish orange coloured dye shows a maximum absorbance at 460 nm. The minimum amount of bromine for bromination was checked by adding varying amount of saturated bromine water. At least 0.2 ml of bromine water was needed for full colour development. Excess of bromine water caused no change in the absorbance since the excess was destroyed with sodium arsenite solution. For the conversion of cyanogenbromide to glutaconic aldehyde, varying amount of pyridine reagent was added. A minimum of 0.2 ml pyridine was needed for the reaction. Constant absorbance values were obtained with the addition of 1–5 ml of sulphanic acid.

It was found that 5–10 min were needed for full colour development. Varying the temperature in the range 15–30° had no serious effect on the final result, and the coloured dye was stable for 25 min. Above 30°, there was decrease in the final absorbance value. The colour system obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.5–3.0 ppm of cyanide. The Sandell's sensitivity was found to be 0.004 0 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The standard and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.014 and 2.7%, respectively.

Effect of foreign ions: To assess the validity of the method the effect of foreign species commonly found with cyanide were studied, by adding known amount of the diverse ion to the standard cyanide solution. The tolerance limit (ppm) of the foreign ions and compounds were found to be as follows: Zn^{II} (100), Cd^{II} (250), Pb^{II} (200), Hg^{II} (100), Na^{I} (500), K^{I} (500), Cu^{II} (350), Fe^{II} (250), Mg^{II} (500), Co^{II} (500), Mn^{II} (300), Fe^{III} (200), Al^{III} (250), benzene (2500), phenol (1000), benzaldehyde (850), ethanol (1500), nitrobenzene (900) and aniline (600). Tolerance limit is the amount of interferent that causes an error of $\pm 2\%$ or less.

Application of the method in biological materials and polluted river water: Several samples of urine and blood were collected and tested, which were free from cyanide. Known amounts of cyanide were added to blood and urine samples and analysed as above and compared with the known Aldridge⁵ method, after the deproteinisation by means of trichloroacetic acid. The river water samples used for cyanide determination were found to be free from cyanide; hence, they were spiked with known amounts of cyanide and analysed with the present method and Aldridge⁵ method, and the recovery was found to be $\sim 100\%$. Results are shown in Table 1.

The proposed method is quick and gives reproducible results. The results of the method is compared with the other reported methods (Table 2).

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SAMPLES OF BLOOD AND URINE AND POLLUTED WATER

Sample*	Cyanide added μg	Cyanide found by present method** μg	Recovery %	Cyanide found by Aldridge method** μg	Recovery %
Blood	5	4.75	95.00	4.80	96.00
	10	9.66	96.00	9.65	96.50
	15	14.90	99.33	14.99	99.90
Urine	5	4.65	93.00	4.68	93.60
	10	9.42	94.20	9.50	95.00
	15	13.95	93.00	14.00	93.33
	20	19.10	95.50	19.05	95.25
Polluted river water	7	6.85	97.80	6.80	97.10
	12	11.90	99.10	12.00	100.00
	18	17.75	98.60	17.90	99.50

*Amount = 1 ml.

**Mean of three replicate analyses.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF METHODS REPORTED FOR THE DETERMINATION OF CYANIDE

Sl. no.	Reagent	λ_{max} nm	Range of determination (ppm)	Remarks
1.	Benzidine ^a	520	0.1–20	Benzidine is carcinogenic
2.	Benzidine ^b	524	0.2–20	Benzidine is carcinogenic
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenylene-diamine ^c	515	0.005–100	<i>p</i> -Phenylene-diamine is carcinogenic
4.	Anthranilic ^d	400	1–7	—
5.	Ag-1, 10-phenanthroline/bromopyrogallol ^e	636	0.26–3	Indirect method
6.	Sulphanilic acid ^f	460	0.5–3	—

^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 8. ^cRef. 12. ^dRef. 16. ^eRef. 14. ^fPresent method.

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